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AN ANNOTATED CHECKLIST OF THE FRUIT FLIES (DIPTERA: TEPHRITIDAE) OF EUROPE

A spreadsheet, originally compiled for the online database Fauna Europaea in 2004, was corrected and updated using critically revised data from published articles, books, and online sources (iNaturalist, Diptera.Info, UkrBIN) before September 30, 2025. This served as the source for a new checklist of the family Tephritidae (Diptera) for Europe, which includes 271 species (267 extant and 3 fossil) across 66 genera (65 extant and 1 fossil). The list provides the distribution by country and region, as well as the most important references for species records from European countries..

Key words: Insecta, Diptera, Tephritidae, fruit flies, checklist, Europe, **Distribution**.

Introduction

With more than 5000 described valid species (Norrbohm, pers. comm.), the Tephritidae (Bulgarian: плодови мухи; Croatian: pjegavokrilke; Czech: vrtulkovití; Danish: frugtfluer; Dutch: boorvliegen; English: true fruit flies; Estonian: puu-viljakärblased; Finnish: porrasperhoset; French: mouches des fruits; German: Bohrfliegen; Greek: μύγα της φρούτων; Hungarian: fúrólegyek; Italian: mosche

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della frutta; Latvian: augu mušas; Lithuanian: marguočiai; Norwegian: borefluer; Polish: nasionnicowate; Portuguese: moscas-da-fruta; Romanian: musculița fructelor; Russian: мухи-пестрокрылки; Slovak: vrtivkovité; Spanish: moscas de la fruta; Swedish: fruktflugor; Ukrainian: осетницеви мухи) is the largest family of acalyptrate Diptera.

European tephritid species are phytophagous, but some primitive Old-World members are saprophagous and live under the bark of fallen trees (Korneyev, 1999) or inside bamboo stems (Dohm et al., 2014). Many tephritid species are fruit-infesting and have economic importance, such as the Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann, 1824), the olive fruit fly *Bactrocera oleae* (Rossi, 1790), the Oriental fruit fly *B. dorsalis* (Hendel, 1912), the European cherry fruit fly *Rhagoletis cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758), the apple maggot *R. pomonella* (Walsh, 1867), the Baluchistan melon fly *Carpomya pardalina* (Bigot, 1891), and many other pests. A few beneficial species are used in biological control programs against weeds (White & Elson-Harris, 1992).

Most tephritids occurring in the Palaearctic Region are phytophagous in composite plants (Asteraceae). Some are stem-borers, like *Orellia falcata* (Scopoli, 1863), *Terellia plagiata* (Dahlbom, 1850), or the asparagus fly *Pliorecepta poeciloptera* (Schrank, 1776). Others cause rhizome or stem galls, such as *Oedaspis multifasciata* (Loew, 1850), *Oxya flavipennis* (Loew, 1844), and *Dithryca guttularis* (Meigen, 1826). However, the larvae of most species feed in the flowerheads, either inducing galls, as *Urophora* spp., feeding inside achenes, or boring within tissues, such as *Terellia* spp. (Korneyev, 1999b; Korneyev et al., 2005; Merz, 1994). Some of them are leaf miners, such as *Philophylla caesio* (Harris, 1780) or *Euleia heraclei* (Linnaeus, 1758). Several species are reported to beinquilines (or even parasites or predators) in the galls of other insects, including sawflies (Hymenoptera, Symphyta), such as *Euphranta toxoneura* (Loew, 1846) (Kopelke, 1984) and possibly a few other European species.

Studies of European tephritid flies were started by Aldrovandi (1602) and Réaumur (1738), but the taxonomic history began with Linnaeus (1758), Scopoli (1763), and Fabricius (1775, 1782, 1794, 1805) and was continued by Meigen (1826, 1830, 1838), Robineau-Desvoidy (1830), Macquart (1835), Loew (1862), Schiner (1864), and Rondani (1870). The most important information on European species appeared in the papers by Hendel (1927), Séguy (1934), Hering (1936 a, 1936 b, 1937 a, 1937 b, 1956), Aczel (1939), Mihalyi (1960), Dirlbek & Dirlbek (1963, 1964 a, 1964 b, 1972), Dirlbek & Dirlbeková (1972), K. Dirlbek (1977, 1982). This information was summarized in the checklists of Diptera of Switzerland (Merz, 1998; Korneyev, 2025); Germany (Merz, 1999), Italy (Belcari et al., 1995; Mazzon & Korneyev, 2021), Czech Republic and Slovakia (Kinkorová, 1997, 2006; Heřman & Kinkorová, 2009), Hungary (Merz, 2000, 2001), Finland (Hackman, 1980; Winqvist & Kahanpää, 2007; Kahanpää & Winqvist, 2014), Spain, Andorra, and Portugal (Merz & Báez, 2002), as well as in manuals of the Tephritidae of the United Kingdom (White, 1988), Switzerland (Merz, 1994), and the Netherlands (Kabos & Aartsen, 1984; Smit, 2010). The data published before 2002, were then summarized by Merz and Korneyev (2004) in the first version of ‘Fauna Europaea’.

The Fauna Europaea project was a public web-service that provided a comprehensive index of scientific names for all extant multicellular European terrestrial and freshwater animals. It served as a unique reference for various communities in science, government, and education. The project comprised about 230,000 taxonomic names, including 130,000 accepted species, far exceeding its initial goal. This immense effort was made possible by over 400 contributing taxonomic specialists from across Europe. The data was delivered according to strict standards and included accepted names, synonyms, taxonomic hierarchy, expert details, and geographical distribution.

The Fauna Europaea project was initially funded by the European Commission from 2000 to 2004, with continued support from several follow-up projects. It was managed by a network of principal partners, and from 2013, the data servers were hosted at the Museum für Naturkunde in Berlin (Pape et al., 2015). This continued until a targeted cyberattack destroyed the museum's servers in mid-October 2023 (MfN, 2024), which affected a significant portion of its digital infrastructure and led to the shutdown of many systems, including the Fauna Europaea site. The site has not been recovered since.

The study area of Fauna Europaea covered the western Palaearctic, including the European mainland, Great Britain, the Macaronesian islands, Cyprus, the Faroe Islands, Iceland, Svalbard, Franz Josef Land, and Novaya Zemlya. It excluded Turkey (Asia Minor), the Caucasus, western Kazakhstan, the Arabian Peninsula, and North Africa (see Fig.).

The dataset (a spreadsheet) for the 2nd version of 'Fauna Europaea' was prepared by 2010 and was based on summarized records and checklists published between 2003 and 2010, along with examined (but unpublished) collection specimens by Merz. The published version (Merz & Korneyev, 2013) was, by mistake, based on the older spreadsheet and did not differ from the 2004 version.

Material and Methods

Further new country records scattered among various articles and faunistic notes (e.g., Merz, 1993; 1996; Kinkorová & Chvála, 2000; Whittington, 2002; Papp, 2003; V. Korneyev, 2003; 2004 a, 2004 b, 2009, 2024, 2025; V. Korneyev & Kameneva, 2006; Smit, 2006 a, 2006 b; Söderman et al. 2007; Miranda et al., 2008; Stucke, 2008; Pintilioaie, 2010 a, 2010 b; V. Korneyev & Evstigneev, 2013; Stalažs, 2014; Korneyev & Kolcsár, 2015; V. Korneyev & S. Korneyev, 2015, 2018; Evstigneev, 2016; V. Korneyev et al., 2017, 2018; Evstigneev & S. Korneyev, 2018; S. Korneyev & V.Korneyev, 2019; Mazzon & V. Korneyev, 2021; Kovac et al., 2022; Babitskiy et al., 2023; Olijar & V. Korneyev, 2023; Shparyk et al., 2023; Kameneva & V. Korneyev, 2024; V. Korneyev & Ilminska, 2024; Brückner, 2025; and many other minor papers, checked if they contain any new country records) are summarized in this work.

The original data spreadsheets prepared for Fauna Europaea version 1 by B. Merz and V. Korneyev (2004) were updated with literature and collection data accumulated by B. Merz until 2009. Further literature records were added to the spreadsheet using a color-coding system to indicate different source groups, with a focus on checklists from various European countries and numerous faunistic papers and notes. These data spreadsheets were used to generate with MS Word merged lists of countries for each species, which were then combined into a single checklist with specified distribution data sources. All

literature data were critically revised by the authors, and a few dubious records based on possible misidentifications are commented on.

A special new source of data was online photo registrations from iNaturalist (2025), UkrBIN (2025), and other resources. All data from UkrBIN were included in the Checklist of Ukrainian Tephritidae (Korneyev, 2024). Every country record on iNaturalist was critically revised and re-identified by the taxonomy experts: Andrii Troshyn (tribe Terelliini), Severyn Korneyev (genus *Tephritis*) and Valery Korneyev (other taxa).

Results

The checklist includes records of 270 species (267 extant and 3 fossil) across 66 genera (65 extant and 1 fossil) of Tephritidae from European countries and their regions. The list is sorted in descending order by species count: Italy (mainland) — 149; France (mainland) — 148; Ukraine — 143; Austria — 125; Germany — 121; Switzerland — 121; Hungary — 115; Czech Republic — 106; Spain (mainland) — 109; Slovakia — 106; Poland — 100; Russia (Central European Region) — 93; Bulgaria — 92; Belgium — 84; Croatia — 82; Greece (mainland) — 82; The Netherlands — 82; Great Britain — 80; Sweden — 77; Russia (East European Region) — 74; Romania — 78; Finland — 71; Lithuania — 71; Denmark (mainland) — 62; Russia (South European Region) — 62; Sicily (Italy) — 61; Norway (mainland) — 60; Albania — 51; Crete — 48; Corsica (France) — 44; Cyprus — 42; Latvia — 42; Moldova — 42; Andorra — 38; Sardinia (Italy) — 37; Ireland — 34; Canary Islands (Spain) — 32; Portugal (mainland) — 32; Russia (Northwest European Region) — 31; Malta — 28; Estonia — 28; Balearic Islands (Spain) — 25; Belarus — 23; Channel Islands (United Kingdom) — 20; Dodecanese (Greece) — 20; Russia (North European Region) — 19; Turkey (European part) — 19; Aegean Islands (Greece) — 18; Luxembourg — 19; Madeira (Portugal) — 17; Slovenia — 17; Serbia — 16; Northern Ireland (United Kingdom) — 15; North Macedonia — 13; Cyclades (Greece) — 10; Bosnia and Herzegovina — 8; Azores (Portugal) — 7; Kaliningrad Region (Russia) — 6; Gibraltar (United Kingdom) — 2; Montenegro — 3; Faroe Islands (Denmark) — 0; Iceland — 0; Liechtenstein — 0; Monaco — 0; Svalbard (Norway) — 0; Savage Islands (Portugal) — 0; Franz Josef Land (Russia) — 0; Novaya Zemlya (Russia) — 0; San Marino — 0; Vatican City — 0.

The highest diversity is observed in countries with the most thoroughly studied faunas, particularly in larger nations that possess a wide variety of habitats, ranging from alpine meadows to arid grasslands. The most species-rich countries include Italy, France, Ukraine, Austria, Germany, and Switzerland. Species diversity shows a clear decline along a latitudinal gradient from south to north.

List of species

This species list has been altered compared to Fauna Europaea, version 1.1 (Merz & Korneyev, 2004) as follows:

1. Species transferred to other nominal genera

Cryptaciura rotundiventris is now considered *Euleia rotundiventris* (see Norrbom et al., 1999).

Paracarphotricha alpestris is now considered *Xanthomyia alpestris* (see Norrbom et al., 1999).

Dioxya bidentis and *Dioxya sororcula* are now considered *Campiglossa bidentis* and *C. sororcula* (see Han & Ro, 2019).

Goniglossum wiedemanni is now considered *Carpomya wiedemanni* (see Korneyev et al., 2017).

Myiopardalis pardalina is now considered *Carpomya pardalina* (see Korneyev et al., 2017).

2. Alien species added to the list

Strauzia longipennis (Wiedemann, 1830), an adventive species, has well-established populations in Germany not eradicated in the last 15 years.

Euaresta aequalis (Loew, 1862) is established in Slovenia and in north-eastern Italy. Both species are North American in origin. Other intercepted alien species, which have no proven established status, are not included in the list.

Tephritis praecox (Loew, 1844). Originally distributed in the Mediterranean region and the Near East, it infests *Calendula* spp. flower heads. It has recently been dispersed via seed material and is now recorded in most Central European countries, occurring predominantly on cultivated flowers.

Terellia fuscicornis (Loew, 1844) is restricted to *Cynara* spp. in the Mediterranean region but was reared from its host plants either planted in a garden or purchased in a market in Scotland and Netherlands (Whittington, 2002; Smit, 2006 a); status of naturalization is uncertain.

Rhagoletis cingulata and *R. completa* are invasive North American species primarily recorded from Switzerland (Merz, 1991) and currently widespread in Western and Central Europe.

3. Fossil species added to the list

Myoacinia adriatica Gentilini & Korneyev, 2006, *Tephritis sophus* Gentilini & Korneyev, 2006, and *Chetostoma? antiqua* (Heer, 1849) were recorded from the Upper Miocene of Italy and the Lower Miocene of Croatia by Gentilini et al. (2006) and are therefore added to the list.

4. Taxonomic and synonymic considerations

We consider all subspecies of *Urophora quadrifasciata* together, as the local complexes of host races can be differentiated only based on reared material and require additional molecular studies (White & Korneyev, 1989).

Campiglossa multiguttata (Dirlbek & Dirlbek, 1969) is considered a junior synonym of *Campiglossa valida* (Wollaston, 1858) by Smit (2006).

Euleia marmorea (Fabricius, 1805) is considered a southwest-Mediterranean colour morph of *E. heraclei* (Linnaeus, 1758) (El Harym & V. Korneyev, in press).

Myopites blotii Brébisson, 1827 includes all reliable data of *M. apicatus* Freidberg, 1982 and a few records of *M. inulaedissentericae* Blot, 1827 from the UK and northern France, according to Korneyev et al. (in press). Dubious, unrevised records are marked with a question mark (?).

Myopites inulae (Roser, 1840) includes most of the data of *M. inulaedissentericae* except for those from the UK and northern France, according to Korneyev et al. (in press). Dubious, unrevised records are marked with a question mark (?).

Myopites longirostris (Loew, 1846) includes the distribution data for the nominal species considered to be its synonyms by Korneyev et al. (in press): *Myopites boghariensis* Séguy, 1934, *M. bonifaciae* Dirlbek, 1973, *M. eximia* Séguy, 1932, *M. frauenfeldi* Schiner, 1863, *M. lelea* Dirlbek, 1973, *M. lelae* Dirlbek, 1974, and *M. zernyi* Hering, 1939. Photo-based re-identification of the Maltese specimens previously identified as *M. variofasciatus* (Vella et al., 2017) shows that they actually belong to *M. longirostris* (V. Korneyev et al., in press).

Myopites tenellus Frauenfeld, 1863 includes the distribution data for the nominal species considered to be its synonym by Korneyev et al. (in press): *Myopites olii* Dirlberk, 1973.

Oedaspis sofiana Drensky, 1943 is a junior synonym of *Myennis octopunctata* (Coquebert, 1798), Ulidiidae (Kameneva & Korneyev, 2014) and does not belong in Tephritidae.

Oedosphearella bob Smit, 2020 is added on the list.

Oxyina nasuta Hering, 1936 is considered a morph of *Oxyina parietina* (Linnaeus, 1758) (V. Korneyev, unpublished data).

Actinoptera espunensis Hering, 1934, described from Sierrade España (Spain) based on the holotype male very similar to *A. meigeni* Hendel, 1927, which is a widespread species in Southern Spain and is considered to be conspecific to the latter (teste B. Merz, unpublished data).

Anastrephoides gerckeii Hendel, 1927, described from “Astrakhan” (southern Russia), was obviously based on a single mislabelled specimen that apparently originated from the Russian Far East. This species belongs to a genus endemic to China, Korea, Japan, and the Russian Far East (V. Korneyev, unpublished data). It is therefore excluded from the list.

Nomenclature and taxonomy generally follows Norrbom et al. (1999), except generic assignment of *Urophora* species following Freidberg & Norrbom (1999) and synonymy of *Myopites* following V. Korneyev et al. (in press).

Checklist with distribution by countries

Acanthophilus helianthi (Rossi, 1794)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Cyclades (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Luxembourg, Moldova, Malta, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Portugal (mainland), Madeira (Portugal), Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Southern Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland, European Turkey,

Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ireland (Byrne, 2022)

Acanthiophilus walkeri (Wollaston, 1858)

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain), Madeira (Portugal) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Acidia cognata (Wiedemann, 1817)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Stalažs, 2014). Belarus, Croatia, Luxembourg, Western Russia, Northern Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovenia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Acinia biflexa (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, France (mainland), Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Southern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Acinia corniculata (Zetterstedt, 1819)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al. 2005). Central Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Aciura coryli (Rossi, 1794)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Spain (mainland), Canary Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Romania, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ireland (Speight, 2000). Czech Republic (Merz, unpubl., leg. Bartak 2007). The Netherlands (Smit & Bruins, 2023). Bosnia & Herzegovina, Croatia, Dodecanese (Greece), North Macedonia, Serbia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Actinoptera discoidea (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution. Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, France (mainland), Hungary, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland, Sweden, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Central Russia (Evstigneev, 2016).

Actinoptera filaginis (Loew, 1862)

Distribution. Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Sweden (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Actinoptera mamulae (Frauenfeld, 1855)

Distribution. Croatia, Cyprus, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Italy (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Actinoptera meigeni Hendel, 1927

Distribution. Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Italy (mainland), Portugal (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Anomoia purmunda (Harris, 1780)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Estonia, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Hungary,

Ireland, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al. 2005; Stalažs, 2014). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Luxembourg, Portugal (mainland), Romania, Western Russia, Southern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Asimoneura stroblii Czerny, 1909

Distribution. Spain (mainland), France (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Bactrocera oleae (Gmelin, 1790)

Distribution. Albania, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Malta, Portugal (mainland), Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Madeira (Portugal) (Smit, 2006; Penado et al., 2020). Croatia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Campiglossa absinthii (Fabricius, 1805)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (Korneyev, 2024) Sicily (Italy) (Mazzon & Korneyev, 2021).

Campiglossa achyrophori (Loew, 1869)

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Poland, Slovakia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2011).

Campiglossa argyrocephala (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Austria, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Sweden, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Baugnée, 2006). Northern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Campiglossa bidentis (RobineauDesvoidy, 1830)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, Malta, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, European Turkey (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Greece (mainland) (Merz, unpublished, leg. Bartak, 2007). Belarus, Croatia, Estonia, Corsica (France), Luxembourg, Portugal (mainland), Western Russia, Southern Russia, Kaliningrad Region (Russia), Serbia, Ukraine (iNaturalist, 2025).

Campiglossa contingens (Becker, 1908)

Distribution. Central Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Campiglossa defasciata (Hering, 1937)

Distribution. Southern Russia (Evsstigneev, 2016).

Campiglossa difficilis (Hendel, 1927)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Norway (mainland), Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al. 2005).

Campiglossa doronici (Loew, 1856)

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, France (mainland), Poland, Romania, Slovakia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2011). Italy (mainland) (Mazzon et al., 2021).

Campiglossa duplex (Becker, 1908)

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Campiglossa freidbergi Merz, 2000

Distribution. Spain (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Campiglossa grandinata (Rondani, 1870)

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Western Russia, Northern Russia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Campiglossa guttella (Rondani, 1870)

Distribution. Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al. 2005). Finland (Söderman et al., 2007).

Campiglossa irrorata (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution. Andorra, Czech Republic, France (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Poland, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al. 2005). Estonia, Central Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Campiglossa loewiana (Hendel, 1927)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Eastern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Campiglossa malaris (Séguy, 1934)

Distribution. Belgium, Germany, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), The Netherlands, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Campiglossa martii (Becker, 1908)

Distribution. Spain (mainland), Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Campiglossa misella (Loew, 1869)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), The Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Southern Russia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Germany (Stuke, 2008). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Lithuania, Latvia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Campiglossa plantaginis (Haliday, 1833)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Hungary, Ireland, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Southern Russia, Sweden, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Central Russia (Evstigneev, 2016).

Campiglossa producta (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Germany; Great Britain (mainland), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Cyclades (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Moldova, Malta, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal (mainland), Azores (Portugal), Madeira (Portugal), Romania, Slovakia, Switzerland, European Turkey, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ireland (Chandler & O'Connor, 2010). Croatia, Southern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Campiglossa punctella (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution. Albania, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, Italy (mainland), Norway (mainland), Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Sicily (Italy) (Mazzon & Korneyev, 2021).

Campiglossa reticulata (Becker, 1908)

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain), Madeira (Portugal) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Campiglossa solidaginis (White, 1986)

Distribution. France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Norway (mainland), Serbia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Czech Republic (Merz, unpublished), Finland (Söderman et al, 2007, Winqvist & Kahanpää, 2007).

Campiglossa sororcula (Wiedemann, 1830)

Distribution. Spain (mainland), Canary Islands (Spain), Azores (Portugal), Madeira (Portugal) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Greece (mainland) (Merz, this work).

Campiglossa valida (Wollaston, 1858)

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain), Madeira (Portugal) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004; Smit, 2006 b).

Capitites ramulosa (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Croatia, Cyprus, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Portugal (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Capparimya savastani (Martelli, 1911)

Distribution. France (mainland), Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Malta (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Balearic Islands (Spain) (Miranda et al. 2008). Cyprus, Balearic Islands (Spain), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Sardinia (Italy) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Carpomya incompleta (Becker, 1903)

Distribution. Italy (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Corsica (France) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Carpomya schineri (Loew, 1856)

Distribution. Austria, Bulgaria, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Baugnée, 2006). Belarus, Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Luxembourg, Romania, Central Russia, Kaliningrad Region (Russia), European Turkey (iNaturalist, 2025).

Carpomya vesuviana Costa, 1854

Distribution. Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Italy (mainland), Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Carpomya pardalina (Bigot, 1891)

Distribution. Cyprus (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (V. Korneyev et al., 2017).

Carpomya wiedemanni (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), The Netherlands, Southern Russia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Montenegro, Romania, Eastern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Ceratitis capitata (Wiedemann, 1824)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Malta, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Portugal (mainland), Azores (Portugal), Madeira (Portugal), Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia, Greece (mainland), Cyclades (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Lithuania, Romania, Western Russia, Southern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Chaetorellia acrolophi White & Marcquart, 1989

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Moldova, North Macedonia, Romania, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Chaetorellia australis Hering, 1940

Distribution. Austria, Bulgaria, Greece (mainland), Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Chaetorellia carthami Stackelberg, 1929

Distribution. Cyprus (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Chaetorellia conjuncta (Becker, 1913)

Distribution. Albania, Greece (mainland), Hungary, European Turkey (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Bulgaria, Romania (iNaturalist, 2025).

Chaetorellia hestia Hering, 1937

Distribution. Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Italy (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Chaetorellia isais Hering, 1937

Distribution. Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Chaetorellia jaceae (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Estonia, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Moldova, North Macedonia, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ireland (Speight, 2000). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Luxembourg, Southern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Chaetorellia loricata (Rondani, 1870)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Moldova, North Macedonia, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Southern Russia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Northern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Chaetorellia succinea (Costa, 1844)

Distribution. Cyprus, France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Italy (mainland), European Turkey (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Chaetostomella baezi Merz, 2000

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Chaetostomella cylindrica (RobineauDesvoidy, 1830)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, Moldova, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Bosnia & Herzegovina, Belarus, Croatia, Estonia, Northern Russia, Southern Russia, Slovenia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Chaetostomella rossica Hendel, 1927

Distribution. Austria, Southern Russia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Germany (Korneyev, 2009).

Chaetostomella steropea (Rondani, 1870)

Distribution. Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Italy (mainland), Malta (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Chaetostomella zhuravlevi Basso, 2000

Distribution. Eastern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Chetostoma curvinerve Rondani, 1856

Distribution. Austria, Germany, Spain (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Serbia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006), The Netherlands (van Aartsen, 2001). Czech Republic, Denmark (iNaturalist, 2025).

Chetostoma stackelbergi (Rohdendorf, 1955)

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), Hungary, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Western Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Finland (Söderman et al, 2007, Winqvist & Kahanpää, 2007). Central Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Chetostoma? antiqua (Heer, 1849 †)

Distribution. Croatia (Gentilini et al., 2006).

Cornutrypeta spinifrons (Schroeder, 1913)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Germany, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Lithuania, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Western Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (Korneyev & Kolcsár, 2015; Korneyev & Korneyev, 2015).

Cornutrypeta superciliata (Frey, 1935)

Distribution. Norway (mainland), Western Russia, Northern Russia, Sweden (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Finland (Söderman et al, 2007; Winqvist & Kahanpää, 2007).

Dithryca guttularis (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Portugal (mainland), Central Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Romania (Pintilioaie, 2010 b). Southern Russia (Evstigneev, 2016).

Serbia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Dithryca guttulosa (Loew, 1869)

Distribution. Spain (mainland), Portugal (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Ensina azorica Frey, 1945

Distribution. Azores (Portugal) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Ensina decisa Wollaston, 1858

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain), Madeira (Portugal) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Ensina sonchi (Linnaeus, 1767)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Moldova, Malta, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Portugal (mainland), Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Belarus, Western Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Euaresta aequalis (Loew, 1862)

Distribution. Italy (mainland), Slovenia (Seljak, 2013).

Euaresta bullans (Wiedemann, 1830)

Distribution. Bulgaria, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Moldova, North Macedonia, Azores (Portugal), Romania, Slovakia, European Turkey, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Corsica (France), Greece (mainland) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Euarestella megacephala (Loew, 1846)

Distribution. Sicily (Italy), Malta (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Euleia heraclei (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, Moldova, Malta, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005; Stalažs, 2014). Romania (Pintilioaie, 2010 a). Bosnia & Herzegovina, Croatia, Estonia, Luxembourg, Portugal (mainland), Northern Russia, Eastern Russia, Southern Russia, Serbia, European Turkey (iNaturalist, 2025).

Euleia rotundiventris (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Euleia separata (Becker, 1908)

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Euphranta connexa (Fabricius, 1794)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Moldova, The Netherlands, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Central Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Euphranta toxoneura (Loew, 1846)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Finland (Söderman et al, 2007, Winqvist & Kahanpää, 2007), Italy (mainland) (Rivosecchi, 2008). Belarus (iNaturalist, 2025).

Eurasimona stigma (Loew, 1840)

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Finland, France (mainland), Hungary, Lithuania, Moldova, North Macedonia, Central Russia, Western Russia, Eastern Russia, Southern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Italy (mainland) (Mazzon et al., 2021). Estonia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Goniurellia longicauda Freidberg, 1980

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain), France (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Spain (mainland) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Goniurellia persignata Freidberg, 1980

Distribution. Cyprus (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Malta (Ebejer & Gatt, 2021).

Hemilea dimidiata (Costa, 1844)

Distribution. Austria, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Central Russia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Slovenia (Korneyev & Kolcsár, 2015). Ukraine (Korneyev & Korneyev, 2015).

Hendrella winnertzi (Frauenfeld, 1864)

Distribution. Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Central Russia (Evstigneev, 2016).

Heringina guttata (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution. Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, Hungary, Lithuania, The Netherlands, Poland, Sweden, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Central Russia (Evstigneev, 2016).

Hypenidium graecum (Loew, 1862)

Distribution. Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Portugal (mainland), Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Ictericodes japonicus (Wiedemann, 1830)

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Eastern Russia, Southern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Ictericodes zelleri (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, France (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Poland, Slovakia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Luxembourg (iNaturalist, 2025).

Inuromaesa maura (Frauenfeld, 1857)

Distribution. Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Hungary, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Italy (mainland) (Mazzon et al., 2021).

Katonaia aida Hering, 1938

Distribution. Aegean Islands (Greece) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Katonaia hemileopsis (Hering, 1947)

Distribution. Crete (Greece) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Merzomyia westermanni (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Belgium, Germany, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Italy (mainland), The Netherlands, Eastern Russia, Southern Russia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Central Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Mioacinia adriatica Gentilini & V. Korneyev, 2006 †

Distribution. Italy (mainland) (Gentilini et al., 2006).

Myoleja lucida (Fallén, 1826)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Western Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2011). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Myopites blotii Brebisson, 1827

Myopites inulaedysenericae Blot, 1827 (part of European records), *M. apicatus* Freidberg 1982.

Distribution. Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), North Macedonia, Slovakia, Switzerland, European Turkey, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006), Germany (this work). The Netherlands (iNaturalist, 2025).

Myopites cypriacus Hering, 1938

Distribution. Cyprus, Aegean Islands (Greece), Sardinia (Italy) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Myopites inulae (Roser, 1840)

Distribution. Germany (Roser, 1840). Austria, Czech Republic, France (mainland) (?), Hungary (?), Italy (mainland) (?), Lithuania, Poland, Romania (?), Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia (?), Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al.,

2022). Estonia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Myopites longirostris (Loew, 1846)

Myopites variofasciatus: (Vella et al., 2017: Malta: misidentification; Ebejer & Gatt, 2021: as *M. longirostris*).

Distribution. Bulgaria (?), Croatia, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Crete (Greece) (?), Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Malta (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Portugal (mainland) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Myopites nigrescens Becker, 1908

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Myopites stylatus (Fabricius, 1794)

Distribution. Albania, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Balearic Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Crete (Greece), Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Slovenia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Greece (mainland) (Korneyev, unpublished). Malta (Ebejer & Gatt, 2021); Spain (mainland), Gibraltar (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Aegean Islands (Greece), Cyclades (Greece), Portugal (mainland) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Myopites tenellus Frauenfeld, 1863

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, France (mainland), Hungary, Slovakia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Romania (Pintilioaie & S. Korneyev, 2010).

Nitrariomyia lukjanovitshi Rohdendorf, 1949

Distribution. Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Noeeta bisetosa Merz, 1992

Distribution. Hungary, Eastern Russia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Italy (mainland) (Mazzon et al., 2021).

Noeeta crepidis Hering, 1936

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Noeeta hemiradiata Dirlbek & Dirlbek, 1991

Distribution. Spain (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Noeeta pupillata (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Montenegro (Merz, unpublished, leg. Bartak, 2007). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Estonia, Luxembourg (iNaturalist, 2025).

Noeeta strigilata (Loew, 1855)

Distribution. Greece (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Bulgaria (Korneyev, in prep.).

Oedaspis dichotoma Loew, 1869

Distribution. Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Oedaspis fissa Loew, 1862

Distribution. Spain (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Oedaspis multifasciata (Loew, 1850)

Distribution. Austria, Croatia, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Italy (mainland), Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Oedaspis quinquefasciata Becker, 1908

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Oedaspis ragdai Hering, 1940

Distribution. Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Oedosphenella bob Smit, 2020

Distribution. Madeira (Portugal) (Penado et al., 2020).

Oedosphenella canariensis (Macquart, 1839)

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Orellia falcata (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), The Netherlands, Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Belarus, Estonia, Lithuania, Romania (iNaturalist, 2025).

Orellia scorzonerae (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Germany, Estonia, France (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Latvia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Orellia stictica (Gmelin, 1790)

Distribution. Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, France (mainland), Hungary, Moldova, Romania, Sweden, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Spain (mainland) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Orellia tragopogonis V. Korneyev & J. Dirlbek, 2003

Distribution. Spain (mainland) (Korneyev, 2003).

Orotava cribrata (Bigot, 1892)

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Oxyaciura tibialis (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Distribution. Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Greece (mainland), Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Madeira (Portugal) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Oxyyna albipila (Loew, 1869)

Distribution. Hungary, Southern Russia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Oxyyna flavipennis (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Channel

Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, North Macedonia, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Ukraine (Korneyev, 2024). Belarus, Northern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Oxya lutulenta Loew, 1869

Distribution. Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Central Russia (Evstigneev, 2016).

Oxya nebulosa (Wiedemann, 1817)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Portugal (mainland), Romania, Central Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Luxembourg (iNaturalist, 2025).

The citation of this species for Liechtenstein (Merz & Korneyev, 2004) is attributable to a technical misprint.

Oxya obesa Loew, 1862

Distribution. Spain (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Oxya parietina (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Oxya variabilis Chen, 1938

Distribution. Southern Russia (Evstigneev, 2016).

Paracanthella pavonina (Portschinsky, 1875)

Distribution. Bulgaria, Southern Russia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Eastern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Philophylla caesio (Harris, 1780)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005; Stalažs, 2014). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Belarus, Romania, Western Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Placaciura alacris (Loew, 1869)

Distribution. Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Platyparea carpathica Kłasa, 2001

Distribution. Poland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Platyparea discoidea (Fabricius, 1787)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania,

Latvia, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Spain (mainland), Luxembourg, Northern Russia, Eastern Russia, Kaliningrad Region (Russia) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Plioreocepta poeciloptera (Schrank, 1776)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Poland, Eastern Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Malta (Ebejer & Gatt, 2021).

Procecidochaes utilis Stone, 1947

Distribution. Madeira (Portugal) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004; Smit, 2006 b). Canary Islands (Spain) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Ptiloedaspis tavaresiana Bezzi, 1920

Distribution. Spain (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Rhagoletis alternata (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ireland (Alexander, 2002), Italy (mainland) (Kohnen et al., 2009). Belarus, Estonia, Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Northern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Rhagoletis batava Hering, 1958

Distribution. Spain (mainland), Italy (mainland), The Netherlands, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006). Lithuania (Stalažs & Balalaikins, 2017). Ukraine (Korneyev, 2024). France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Kaliningrad Region (Russia) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Rhagoletis berberidis Jermy, 1961

Distribution. Austria, Hungary, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Italy (mainland) (Mazzon et al., 2021).

Rhagoletis cerasi (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, Latvia, Moldova, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Portugal (mainland), Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Southern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Malta (Ebejer & Gatt, 2021). Bosnia & Herzegovina, Belarus, Aegean Islands (Greece), Cyclades (Greece), Luxembourg, Serbia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Rhagoletis cingulata (Loew, 1862)

Distribution. Germany, Italy (mainland), The Netherlands, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006), Croatia (Bjeliš, M. & Seljak, 2008; Bjeliš & Buljubašić, 2016). Great Britain (mainland) (Bowyer, 2016). Denmark, Lithuania, Poland (iNaturalist, 2025).

Rhagoletis completa Cresson, 1929

Distribution. Italy (mainland), Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Slovenia (Seljak, 1999). Croatia (Duso & Dal Lago, 2006), Germany (EPPO, 2009; Höfken, 2011; Polzin,

2024; Bruckner, 2025), Austria, France (mainland) (Aluja et al., 2011). The Netherlands (Smit & Schaareman, 2015). Bosnia & Herzegovina, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Hungary, Sicily (Italy), Poland, Romania (iNaturalist, 2025).

Rhagoletis flavicincta Enderlein, 1934

Distribution. Central Russia, Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (Korneyev et al. 2017).

Rhagoletis meigenii (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 1996). Finland (iNaturalist, 2025).

Rhagoletis merzi S. Korneyev et al., 2022

Distribution. Switzerland (Korneyev et al., 2022).

Rhagoletis zernyi Hendel, 1927

Distribution. Spain (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Spathulina sicula Rondani, 1856

Distribution. Croatia, Cyprus, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Cyclades (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Malta, Portugal (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Sardinia (Italy) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Sphaeniscus filiulus (Loew, 1869)

Distribution. Spain (mainland), Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Sphenella marginata (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Cyclades (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, Moldova, Malta, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Portugal (mainland), Azores (Portugal), Madeira (Portugal), Romania, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, European Turkey, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Finland (Söderman et al., 2007). Belarus, Estonia, Luxembourg, Central Russia, Western Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Stemonocera cornuta (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution. Austria, Germany, Great Britain (mainland), Italy (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006), Hungary (Papp, 2003). Bulgaria, Romania (Korneyev & Kolcsár, 2015). Croatia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Stemonocera spinulosa (Hering, 1936)

Distribution. Germany, Poland, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Strauzia longipennis (Wiedemann, 1830)

Distribution. Germany (Brückner & Korneyev, 2010).

Tephritis acanthiophilopsis Hering, 1938

Distribution. Czech Republic, Hungary, Italy (mainland), Romania, Slovakia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). The Netherlands (Smit & Aartsen, 2007). Germany, Southern Russia (S. Korneyev, 2016).

Tephritis angustipennis (Loew, 1857)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Finland, France (mainland), The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Southern Russia (Evstigneev, 2016). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2016).

Tephritis arnicae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Moldova, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2011). Greece (mainland), Central Russia (S. Korneyev, 2016).

Tephritis bardanae (Schrank, 1803)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Belarus, Estonia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Western Russia, Northern Russia, Southern Russia, Kaliningrad Region (Russia), Slovenia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Tephritis brachyura Loew, 1869

Distribution. Eastern Russia, Southern Russia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Tephritis carmen Hering, 1937

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Italy (mainland), Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Tephritis cometa (Loew, 1840)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Moldova, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Western Russia (S. Korneyev, 2016). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Portugal (mainland), Southern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Tephritis conura (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Estonia, Western Russia, Northern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

***Tephritis conyzifoliae* Merz, 1992**

Distribution. Czech Republic, France (mainland), Eastern Russia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Austria (Merz, unpublished, leg. Kofler, 2007). Germany (Korneyev, 2004 a). Central Russia, Southern Russia (Evstigneev, 2016). Western Russia, Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2016; S. Korneyev & Klasa, 2016). Italy (mainland) (Mazzon et al., 2021).

***Tephritis crepidis* Hendel, 1927**

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), The Netherlands, Poland, Central Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Romania (S. Korneyev, 2016).

***Tephritis dilacerata* (Loew, 1846)**

Distribution. Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Belarus, Estonia, Western Russia (S. Korneyev, 2016). Southern Russia (Evstigneev, 2016). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Lithuania (iNaturalist, 2025).

***Tephritis dioscurea* (Loew, 1856)**

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Moldova, The Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Greece (mainland) (Merz, unpublished, leg. Bartak, 2007). Southern Russia (Evstigneev, 2016).

Western Russia, Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2016). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

***Tephritis divisa* Rondani, 1871**

Distribution. Croatia, Cyprus, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Great Britain (mainland) (Hodge, 2006; Chandler, 2007), Ukraine (Korneyev, 2003). Germany (S. Korneyev, 2016).

***Tephritis dudichi* Aczel, 1939**

Distribution. Bulgaria, Romania, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004); Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2011).

***Tephritis fallax* (Loew, 1844)**

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Estonia, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), The Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006), Finland (Söderman et al., 2007; Winqvist & Kahanpää, 2007). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Lithuania (S. Korneyev, 2016).

***Tephritis formosa* (Loew, 1844)**

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Moldova, Malta, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal (mainland), Romania, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Montenegro (Merz, unpublished, leg. Bartak, 2007). Croatia, Luxembourg, Slovenia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Tephritis frauenfeldi Hendel, 1927

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Romania (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). France (mainland) (S. Korneyev, 2016). Sicily (Italy), Sardinia (Italy) (Mazzon & Korneyev, 2021). The source of reference from Slovakia is unknown; it is not on the list in Heřman & Kinkorová (2009).

Tephritis heliophila Hendel, 1927

Distribution. Austria, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Italy (mainland), Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2016; S. Korneyev & Klasa, 2016).

Tephritis hendeliana Hering, 1944

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Albania (S. Korneyev, 2016). Southern Russia (Evsstigneev, 2016).

Tephritis hungarica Hering, 1937

Distribution. Romania, Serbia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Greece (mainland) (S. Korneyev, 2016).

Tephritis hurvitzii Freidberg, 1982

Distribution. Cyprus, Greece (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (Korneyev, 2003; Korneyev et al., 2021 b). Southern Russia (S. Korneyev & Nikelshparg, 2015; S. Korneyev, 2016).

Tephritis hyoscyami (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Portugal (mainland), Romania, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Greece (mainland), Moldova (S. Korneyev, 2016). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Southern Russia (Evsstigneev, 2016). Belarus, Estonia, Luxembourg, Central Russia, Western Russia, Northern Russia, Eastern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Tephritis leontodontis (De Geer, 1776)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Ireland, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Estonia, Latvia, Central Russia, Western Russia (S. Korneyev, 2016). Sicily (Italy) (?) (Mazzon & Korneyev, 2021).

Tephritis luteipes Merz, 1992

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Tephritis maccus Hering, 1937

Distribution. France (mainland), Italy (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Tephritis mariannae Merz, 1992

Distribution. France (mainland), Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Tephritis matricariae (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (main-

land), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), The Netherlands, Portugal (mainland), Slovakia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ireland (Byrne, 2022). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Luxembourg (iNaturalist, 2025).

Tephritis mutabilis Merz, 1992

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, France (mainland), Poland, Slovakia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Finland (Söderman et al., 2007). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2016; S. Korneyev & Klasa, 2016). Italy (mainland) (Mazzon et al., 2021).

Tephritis neesii (Meigen, 1830)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia, Estonia, Greece (mainland) Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2016). Central Russia (Evstigneev, 2016). Northern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Tephritis nigricauda (Loew, 1856)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Malta, Poland, Portugal (mainland), Romania, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Central Russia (Evstigneev, 2016). Slovakia (S. Korneyev, 2016).

Tephritis oedipus Hendel, 1927

Distribution. Southern Russia, Ukraine (S. Korneyev & Karpyuk, 2009; Evstigneev, 2016).

Tephritis postica (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Moldova, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Denmark, Southern Russia, Serbia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Tephritis praecox (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Malta, The Netherlands, Portugal (mainland), Madeira (Portugal), Romania, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Merz, unpublished, leg. Bartak, 2007), Slovakia (Korneyev et al. 2021 a). Germany, Denmark, Poland, Serbia, European Turkey (iNaturalist, 2025).

Tephritis pulchra (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Poland, Slovakia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (?) (Karpa et al., 2005). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2016). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Tephritis recurrens Loew, 1869

Distribution. Albania, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Italy (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Tephritis ruralis (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Central Russia (Evstigneev, 2016). Estonia, Lithuania, Western Russia (S. Korneyev, 2016). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Tephritis rydeni Hering, 1956

Distribution. Sweden (Hering, 1956). Finland (Söderman et al., 2007, Winqvist & Kahanpää, 2007). Western Russia (S. Korneyev, 2016).

Tephritis santolinae Hering, 1934

Distribution. Cyprus, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Sardinia (Italy) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Tephritis sauterina Merz, 1994

Distribution. Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Tephritis scorzonerae Merz, 1993

Distribution. Spain (mainland), Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Tephritis separata Rondani, 1871

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), The Netherlands, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Southern Russia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2016).

Tephritis simplex (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Croatia, Cyprus, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Portugal (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Tephritis sophus Gentilini & V. Korneyev, 2006 †

Distribution. Italy (mainland) (Gentilini et al., 2006).

Tephritis stictica Loew, 1862

Distribution. Albania, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Crete (Greece), Cyclades (Greece), Italy (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Portugal (mainland) (Almeida & S. Korneyev, 2010). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Tephritis tanacetii Hering, 1956

Distribution. Austria, Germany, France (mainland), Hungary, Slovakia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006). Central Russia (Evstigneev, 2016). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2016; S. Korneyev & Klasa, 2016).

Tephritis truncata (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Italy (mainland), Poland, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Tephritis valida (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Moldova, Romania, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Tephritis vespertina (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Malta, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Portugal (mainland), Slovakia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2011). Bosnia & Herzegovina, Croatia (S. Korneyev, 2016).

Tephritis zernyi Hendel, 1927

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Bulgaria, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Slovakia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Czech Republic (Merz, unpublished). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Tephritomyia lauta (Loew, 1869)

Distribution. Cyprus, Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Cyclades (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Terellia ceratocera (Hendel, 1913)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Ukraine (Korneyev, 2024). Western Russia, Southern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Terellia clarissima V. Korneyev, 1987

Distribution. Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Terellia cyanooides V. Korneyev, 2003

Distribution. Ukraine (Korneyev, 2003).

Terellia cynarae (Rondani, 1870)

Distribution. Italy (mainland) (Rondani, 1870).

Terellia euura (Hering, 1942)

Distribution. Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Terellia gynaecochroma (Hering, 1937)

Terellia lappae auctt., non Cederhjelm (1798).

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Moldova, Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Western Russia, Eastern Russia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Southern Russia, European Turkey (iNaturalist, 2025). The Slovakian record (Merz & Korneyev, 2024) is unconfirmed and absent from Heřman & Kinkorová (2009). Reports of this species being reared from *Onopordum* flower heads in Crete (Neuenschwander & Freidberg, 1983) likely belong to a different taxon, as all other reared material has been obtained exclusively from stem-boring larvae.

Terellia nigronota (V. Korneyev, 1985)

Distribution. Central Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (Korneyev, 2024)

Terellia plagiata (Dahlbom, 1850)

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Lithuania, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006), Finland (Söderman et al., 2007; Winqvist & Kahanpää, 2007). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Terellia rhapontici Merz, 1990

Distribution. Italy (mainland), Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Terellia setifera Hendel, 1927

Distribution. Austria, Bulgaria, Hungary, Central Russia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Terellia tussilaginis (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Estonia, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Western Russia, Eastern Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Ireland (Alexander, 2009). Belarus, Croatia, Southern Russia, Kaliningrad Region (Russia), Slovenia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Terellia amberboae V. Korneyev & Merz, 1996

Distribution. Central Russia (Korneyev & Evstigneev, 2007).

Terellia colon (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, Moldova, The Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Finland (Söderman et al., 2007). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Terellia fuscicornis (Loew, 1844)

Distribution. Cyprus, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Malta (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Great Britain (mainland) (Whittington, 2002). The Netherlands (Smit, 2006 a). European Turkey (iNaturalist, 2025).

Terellia longicauda (Meigen, 1838)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Bagnée, 2006), The Netherlands (Smit, 2006 a). Croatia, Greece (mainland), Southern Russia, Serbia, Slovenia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Terellia luteola (Wiedemann, 1830)

Distribution. Spain (mainland), Crete (Greece), Italy (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Terellia odontolophi V. Korneyev, 1993

Distribution. Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Central Russia, Southern Russia (Evstigneev, 2016).

Terellia orheana V. Korneyev, 1990

Distribution. Moldova, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Terellia pseudovirens (Hering, 1940)

Also as *T. vectensis* (Collin, 1937), questionable synonymy.

Distribution. Cyprus (Merz & Korneyev, 2004), Ukraine (Korneyev, 1982).

Terellia ruficauda (Fabricius, 1794)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Belarus, Estonia, Portugal (mainland), Western Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Terellia sabroskyi Freidberg, 1982

Distribution. Crete (Greece) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Terellia serratulae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Moldova, Malta, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Portugal (mainland), Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, European Turkey, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Croatia, Estonia, Southern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Terellia uncinata White, 1989

Distribution. Albania, Bulgaria, Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Aegean Islands (Greece), Italy (mainland), European Turkey (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Terellia vectensis (Collin, 1937)

Also as *Terellia oasis* (Hering, 1938), and *T. pseudovirens* (Hering, 1940), questionable synonymy.

Distribution. Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Italy (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Portugal (mainland) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Terellia virens (Loew, 1846)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Terellia winthemi (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia,

Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Greece (mainland) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Terellia zerovae Korneyev, 1985

Distribution. Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Romania (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Trupanea amoena (Frauenfeld, 1857)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Moldova, Malta, Poland, Portugal (mainland), Madeira (Portugal), Romania, Slovakia, Switzerland, European Turkey, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa, 2008), The Netherlands (Smit & Hamers, 2006). Gibraltar (United Kingdom) (iNaturalist, 2025).

Trupanea cosmia (Schiner, 1868)

Distribution. Madeira (Portugal) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Trupanea guimari (Becker, 1908)

Distribution. Spain (mainland), Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Trupanea insularum (Becker, 1908)

Distribution. Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Trupanea stellata (Fuesslin, 1775)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Cyclades (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, Moldova, Malta, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Azores (Portugal), Madeira (Portugal), Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022). Southern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Trupanea tubulata Munro, 1964

Distribution. Balearic Islands (Spain), Canary Islands (Spain) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Trypeta artemisiae (Fabricius, 1794)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Ukraine (Korneyev & Korneyev, 2015). Eastern Russia (Evstigneev, 2016). Ireland (Chandler, 2025). Belarus, Central Russia, Slovenia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Trypeta immaculata (Macquart, 1835)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Ireland, Italy (mainland), The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (Korneyev & Korneyev, 2015). Central Russia, Northern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Trypeta zoe Meigen, 1826

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belarus (Korneyev, 2003). Ukraine (Korneyev & Korneyev, 2015). Estonia, Corsica (France), Portugal (mainland), Central Russia, Western Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Urophora affinis (Frauenfeld, 1857)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Moldova, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora aprica (Fallén, 1814)

Distribution. Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, Poland, Central Russia, Western Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora cardui (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Moldova, North Macedonia, The Netherlands, Poland, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ireland (Fitzpatrick & O'Halloran, 2009). Belarus, Estonia, Luxembourg, Norway (mainland), Romania, Western Russia, Northern Russia (iNaturalist, 2025).

Urophora christophi (Loew, 1869)

Distribution. Central Russia, Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora congrua (Loew, 1862)

Distribution. Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, France (mainland), Italy (mainland), Poland, Romania, Slovakia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine (S. Korneyev, 2011).

Urophora coronata Basso, 1990

Distribution. Eastern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora cuspidata (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Lithuania, Moldova, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Spain (mainland), Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Belgium (Baugnée, 2006). Italy (mainland) (Mazzon et al., 2021).

Urophora dzieduszyckii Frauenfeld, 1867

Distribution. Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora hispanica Strobl, 1905

Distribution. Spain (mainland), France (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora impicta (Hering, 1942)

Distribution. Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora jaceana (Hering, 1935)

Distribution. Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, North Macedonia, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Western Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Urophora jaculata Rondani, 1870

Distribution. Croatia, Greece (mainland), Italy (mainland) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora kasachstanica (Richter, 1964)

Distribution. Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Southern Russia (Evstigneev & Boyko, 2025).

Urophora korneyevi White, 1998

Distribution. Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora longicauda (Hendel, 1927)

Distribution. Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora lopholomae Korneyev & White, 1989

Distribution. Austria, Hungary, Moldova, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Urophora mauritanica Macquart, 1851

Distribution. Albania, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Spain (mainland), Balearic Islands (Spain), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Moldova, North Macedonia, Malta, Southern Russia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora neuenschwanderi Freidberg, 1982

Distribution. Crete (Greece) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora pauperata (Zaitzev, 1945)

Distribution. Albania, European Turkey (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora phalolepidis Merz & White, 1991

Distribution. Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora pontica (Hering, 1937)

Distribution. Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora quadrifasciata (Meigen, 1826)

Distribution. Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Central Russia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Eastern Russia, Estonia, France (mainland), Germany, Great Britain (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Lithuania, Malta, Moldova, The Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Sicily (Italy), Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Urophora sirunaseva (Hering, 1938)

Distribution. Greece (mainland), Crete (Greece), Dodecanese (Greece), Hungary, Moldova, European Turkey, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora solstitialis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, Moldova, The Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Northern Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Urophora spoliata (Haliday, 1838)

Distribution. France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Hungary, Slovakia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora stylata (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Corsica (France), Great Britain (mainland), Crete (Greece), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, Moldova, The Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Northern Russia, Eastern Russia, Southern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, European Turkey, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Norway (mainland) (Greve, 2008). Latvia (Karpa et al., 2005). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Urophora tenuis (Becker, 1908)

Distribution. Southern Russia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora terebrans (Loew, 1850)

Distribution. Albania, Austria, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Spain (mainland), France (mainland), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Italy (mainland), Sicily (Italy), Moldova, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Croatia (Kovac et al., 2022).

Urophora trinervii Korneyev & White, 1996

Distribution. Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora variabilis (Loew, 1869)

Distribution. Greece (mainland), Moldova, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Southern Russia, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Urophora vera Korneyev & White, 1996

Distribution. Ukraine (Kameneva & Korneyev, 2024).

Urophora xanthippe (Munro, 1934)

Distribution. Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Southern Russia (Evstigneev & Boyko, 2025).

Xanthomyia alpestris (Pokorny, 1887)

Distribution. Austria, Finland, Italy (mainland), Latvia, Northern Russia, Eastern Russia, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Spain (mainland) (Korneyev, 2004 b).

***Xyphosia laticauda* (Meigen, 1826)**

Distribution. Austria, France (mainland), Hungary, Switzerland (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Italy (mainland) (Mazzon et al., 2021).

***Xyphosia miliaria* (Schrank, 1781)**

Distribution. Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain (mainland), Finland, France (mainland), Great Britain (mainland), Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Channel Islands (United Kingdom), Greece (mainland), Hungary, Ireland, Italy (mainland), Sardinia (Italy), Sicily (Italy), Lithuania, Moldova, The Netherlands, Norway (mainland), Poland, Romania, Central Russia, Eastern Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004).

Figure 1. Countries and their regions of Europe. Figure 2. Regions of European Russia.

Acronyms of names of European states or their regions as shown on the maps: AD — Andorra; AL — Albania; AT — Austria; BA — Bosnia and Herzegovina; BE — Belgium; BG — Bulgaria; BY — Belarus; CH — Switzerland; CY — Cyprus; CZ — Czech Republic; DE — Germany; DK-DEN — Denmark; EE — Estonia; ES-BAL — Balearic Islands (Spain); ES-CNY — Canary Islands (Spain); ES-SPA — Spain (mainland); FI — Finland; FR-COR — Corsica (France); FR-FRA — France (mainland); GB-CI — Channel Islands (Great Britain); GB-GI — Gibraltar (Great Britain); GB-GRB — Great Britain (mainland); GB-NI — Northern Ireland (Great Britain); GR-AEG — Aegean Islands (Greece); GR-CYC — Cyclades (Greece); GR-DOD — Dodecanese (Greece); GR-GRC — Greece (mainland); GR-KRI — Crete (Greece); HR — Croatia; HU — Hungary; IE — Ireland; IS — Iceland; IT-ITA — Italy (mainland); IT-SAR — Sardinia (Italy); IT-SIC — Sicily (Italy); LT — Lithuania; LU — Luxembourg; LV — Latvia; MD — Moldova; ME — Montenegro; MK — North Macedonia; MT — Malta; NL — Netherlands; NO-NOR — Norway (mainland); PL — Poland; PT-AZO — Azores (Portugal); PT-MDR — Madeira (Portugal); PT-POR — Portugal (mainland); RO — Romania; RS — Serbia; RU-KGD — Kaliningrad Province (Russia); RU-RUC — Central Russia; RU-RUE — East Russia; RU-RUN — North Russia; RU-RUS — South Russia; RU-RUW — West Russia; SE — Sweden; SI — Slovenia; SK — Slovakia; TR-TUE — European Turkey; UA — Ukraine. Some countries (e.g., Liechtenstein, Monaco, San Marino) and regions, for which there are no records in the checklist, are not indicated on the map. The Azores, Madeira, and Canary Islands are located outside the map boundaries.

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АНОТОВАНИЙ СПИСОК ОСЕТНИЦЕВИХ МУХ (DIPTERA: TEPHRITIDAE) ЄВРОПИ.

Електронну таблицю, початково складену для онлайн-бази даних Fauna Europaea у 2004 році, виправлено та оновлено з використанням критично перевірених даних із опублікованих статей, книг та онлайн-джерел (iNaturalist, Diptera.Info, UkrBIN) станом на 30 вересня 2025 року. Вона стала основою для нового списку видів родини Tephritidae (Diptera) Європи, який включає 271 вид (267 сучасних та 3 викопних) у межах 66 родів (65 сучасних та 1 викопний). Список містить дані про поширення за країнами та регіонами, а також найважливіші літературні посилання на знахідки видів у країнах Європи.

Ключові слова: Insecta, Diptera, Tephritidae, осетниці мухи, список видів, Європа, поширення..

Supplementary files:

[Table 1. Distributional records of European Tephritidae by country and region \(updated September 30, 2025\)](#)

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